

CROSS-COUNTRY COMPARISON OF EFFECTIVE METHODS OF MANAGING PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. The article discusses the quality of pre-school education. The actuality of the present investigation is grounded by the fact that the problems of organization and management of preschool educational establishment are in the order of the day yet, because it is clear when the education of children is well organized in the primary grades positive results can be achieved in the upper grades. The aim of the article is to analyze and give a detailed description of the pupils' attitudes to learning that are different, especially, primary school pupils have their own aspects of work, what creates a number of difficulties in the organization of educational work.

Keywords: management, planning, organization, activity, opportunity, private categories, organization, leadership, control, efficiency, quality of education, knowledge, awareness.

МЕЖСТРАНОВОЕ СРАВНЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНЫХ МЕТОДОВ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ДОШКОЛЬНЫМИ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫМИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯМИ

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается качество дошкольного образования. Актуальность настоящего исследования обусловлена тем, что проблемы организации и управления дошкольным образовательным учреждением пока стоят на повестке дня, поскольку ясно, что при правильно организованном обучении детей в начальных классах можно добиться положительных результатов. быть достигнуто в старших классах. Цель статьи - проанализировать и дать подробную характеристику отношения учащихся к учебе, которые различны, особенно у учеников начальных классов, имеют свои особенности работы, что создает ряд трудностей в организации воспитательной работы.

Ключевые слова: управление, планирование, организация, деятельность, возможность, частные категории, организация, лидерство, контроль, эффективность, качество образования, знания, осведомленность.

Literary review. The scientific literature outlines the general characteristics of management in education management: 1. Management is the activity of entities that ensure the purposefulness and organization of the work of people in any institution. 2. The management of any social organization may be aimed at the creation, establishment, operation and development of that organization. 3. Management is carried out through four management actions: planning, organizing, directing and controlling. 4. Management in any field can be effective if it is goal-

oriented, systematic, predictable, periodic. 5. Management can be effective in any field of activity if it meets the following requirements: a) the control mechanism corresponds to the complexity of the object and the capabilities of the subject; b) sufficient resources (time, management solutions, etc.) are available; c) the criteria are chosen correctly; g) has a well-developed feedback system; d) taking into account the human factor, etc. 6. Management of any social organization can be fully designed, described and implemented through management functions, organizational structures and organizational mechanisms.

Main part. (Methodology, results). Today, the reform of pre-school education is one of the issues at the level of public policy in the upbringing of children who are mature, morally harmonious, aesthetically and physically developed. The pedagogical process in preschool education is a goal-oriented, organizationally formed and content-rich system under the influence of pedagogical activity. Measures such as finding new ways to manage this system and improving its quality, equipping the educational process with modern technologies, its spiritual renewal, structural and technical and technological restructuring are important.

The multifaceted and complex nature of the problem of forming a comprehensively mature person shows its importance for modern educational theory and practice. Because this task cannot be fulfilled without the skills of teachers, their maturity, deep professional knowledge, skills and abilities, special knowledge. In this regard, it is important to increase the professional competence of teachers in educational institutions.

This makes it necessary to train specialists who meet the requirements of the time in the preschool education system, as well as theoretical knowledge, in accordance with international standards. At the same time, one of the main conditions for the reform of preschool education is to cultivate a generation of professionals who have great spiritual qualities, human qualities and work as a mature staff. This requirement of the modern world requires the preschool to fulfill the task of educating pupils as morally and spiritually mature people. One of the most important tasks facing the leaders and teachers of preschool education establishments is the formation of a free civic spirit, a free person. ¹In other words, a free person who recognizes his rights, understands his own strengths and capabilities, has an independent approach to the events and happenings around him, and at the same time builds his personal interests in accordance with the interests of the country and the people. It is necessary to bring up harmoniously developed people. In this sense, educating a perfect person requires, first of all, great skill and responsibility from educators. There is no ready-made example or model for the art of teaching and mentoring. It takes a lot of energy, creativity and many years of experience to master this art. Pedagogical and psychological bases of preschool education system, pedagogical conditions of organization of state and non-state preschool educational organizations and their alternative types, legal and normative bases of organization of preschool educational organizations, content of anti-corruption education, management and the development of world experience and technologies for its application in the educational process is accelerating.

The World Conference on the issues of education and education of young children was held in Tashkent. On November 15, President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev attended this

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conference. The conference aims to define policies in the world regarding preschool education by 2030 and to expand international cooperation in this regard. It is attended by the Director General of UNESCO Audrey Azul, ministers and representatives from about 150 countries, officials of international organizations.

Previously, the coverage rate of preschool education in our country had fallen by 27 percent. There were no modern manuals in kindergartens, the buildings were repaired.

Therefore, the head of state paid special attention to this link and determined the policy of raising a harmonious generation precisely from a young age. In accordance with the decree of the president of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2017, the Ministry of preschool education was established. Much work began on the construction and repair of kindergartens, the introduction of advanced educational methods and methodologies. There was also an opportunity for private sector penetration to develop the industry. Subsidies were established at the expense of the state budget for each foster child. Thousands of family nurseries were established in remote and remote areas. As a result, in recent years, the number of preschool institutions has increased by 6 times. The number of educators and educators also increased by 3 times to 160,000. Thus, out of 2,800,000 children of kindergarten age, 2,000,000 were covered by preschool education. The head of state also touched on the issue of continuity in the educational system. Grown from our land

"We are putting the issue of building a third renaissance in our country before us as a strategic task, raising it to the level of a national idea. We know that preschool education and school education, the higher education system and scientific and cultural institutions are four continuous rings of the future Renaissance. We consider our kindergarten educator, school teacher, professors and scientific and creative intellectuals to be the four pillars of the New Renaissance, " the president said

- This is being worked on harmoniously combining national experience and advanced achievements in the world. Continuing this consistently, it is planned to bring the child preschool coverage rate to 80% in 2025. I compared with other advanced countries, taking into account this

Due to the management, planning and organization of the preschool educational organization, the necessary, but not sufficient, conditions are created to effectively unite the efforts of the team members of the educational organization. It is known from practice that the work people do in reality does not always correspond to the official requirements imposed on them. A special feature of social organizations is that people who are part of them have their own reasons and are able to set goals for themselves. They may or may not want to do something and act accordingly. When people come to an organization, they want it to enable them to realize their interests. If this does not happen, they either leave the organization or do not fully mobilize their potential and talents.

If joint activities are well planned and organized, performers it is some internal and external condition that requires adjustment to the process only when they know what, where and how to do it until it changes will be successful. These changes can threaten the implementation of planned actions or, on the contrary, open some new opportunities.

The timely reaction of the management to the changes that are taking place and for that, he should have information about it. Get such information and work so-called control to determine

the need to make adjustments to the progress it is necessary to implement a special management action

Management is the most important component without which it cannot function due to control part will have feedback. Control is the "clear eye" of management and it sounds impressive about the changes. The reaction to these changes through planning, organizing and leading. As a result, the control circuit becomes closed. Planning, organizing, directing and controlling are complex has a structure, and it is composed of many other works. For example, he planning, situation analysis, forecasting, goal setting, efficiency evaluation, making a decision about choosing any option of the work plan, etc may include. Assigning tasks to employees under management, analysis of the team situation, evaluation of the work of subordinates, awarding and making decisions about punishment, informing employees, resolving conflict situations to do and envisions. There is not one, but many management categories in the management of an educational organization is done. These categories have a hierarchical structure - relative to private categories included in general. For example, the educational process in an educational organization planning of elementary and general secondary education in the general category of management, categories of organization, leadership and control are distinguished. This categories, in turn, have a complex structure. For example, primary education within the management group and planning the study of some classes, subjects, categories of organization, leadership, and control are distinguished.

In the management process, at the same time, the work of various management groups is carried out is increased. Someone makes corrections to the training schedule, someone is the teacher supervise the work, and someone else the work plan of the pedagogic council can discuss.

It is not only the uninformed observer of the ruling class for, but also for most management entities.²

But the head of the educational organization is responsible for the integrity of management should create these categories and monitor each of them.

For example, if the educational organization has an excellent material base, of financing teachers in other educational organizations at the expense of additional resources he was deprived of all these benefits even though he could pay relatively higher wages ensure that the quality of education is higher than in a regular educational organization possible. But the problem is that each educational organization has its own opportunities how well it is used.

Assessment of management quality depends on the answer to this question.

Management is full of opportunities to get useful results according to its mission must ensure use. The better he does this task, the better he is it will be so effective.

Effectiveness of management is achieved and achievable we understand the characteristic that reflects the relationship between productivity.

Such a definition is related to the management of activities and development can also be used in relation to management. But each of these cases is different results and various costs must be considered. Educational organization is education for itself can ensure that the quality is as high as possible (this is high efficiency and may indicate

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management of activity), but at the same time it in an objective way to absorb news and strengthen one's potential may not use the available opportunities of education. This is an educational organization indicates the low efficiency of development management. Development of awareness of the quality of education among young people providing various aspects of educational activities, teaching content, forms and methods, material and technical base, staff structure and description determined by the sum of indicators. In short, in discussing the policy and program context in which ECEC has developed, multiple factors have contributed to the development of a highly fragmented delivery system that is clearly not yet fully responsive to the dramatic social and demographic changes that have occurred in the society.

Moreover, the US is world renowned for its extensive and rigorous child development research. In this context it is even more surprising how extensive a gap there is between the state of knowledge regarding child development and child well-being on the one hand, and the public policy response as reflected in national ECEC policies, on the other. American society has long been conflicted in its attitude towards women and their proper roles and in its attitude towards government and the family and their appropriate roles. This tension emerges repeatedly in discussions regarding ECEC policies. Poor single mothers are expected to work outside the home and, despite a very different reality, there are many who still believe that middle class mothers should remain at home. The conflict between a family's goal to be self-sufficient and women's responsibility to nurture her children and family remains unresolved and penetrates public policy discussions regularly. Government's involvement in the rearing of children is still viewed by some as trespassing into the private lives of its citizens. Child care and early education developed separately, historically, and are still not well integrated. Despite research demonstrating that high quality early childhood care and education can be beneficial to children, research has also demonstrated that the majority of children in the United States are placed in low quality care, some of which may be detrimental to the long-term development of children (NICHD, 1998). This Country Note for the United States of America is an output of the OECD Thematic Review of Early Childhood Education and Care Policy. The review project was launched by the OECD's Education Committee in March 1998 following the 1996 Ministerial meeting on Making Lifelong Learning a Reality for All. In their communiqué, the Education Ministers of the OECD member countries assigned a high priority to the goals of improving access to early childhood education and care, and of improving the quality of early childhood provision (OECD, 1996). In partnership with families, both are central aspects of strengthening the foundations of lifelong learning. The goal of the review is to provide cross-national information to improve policy-making in early childhood education and care in all OECD countries.

2. The USA is one of 12 countries participating in the review between 1998 and 2000. The other countries are Australia, Belgium, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Sweden, and the United Kingdom. These countries provide a diverse range of social, economic and political contexts, as well as varied policy approaches towards the education and care of young children.

3. The scope of the review covers children from birth to compulsory school age, including the transition to primary schooling. In order to analyses what children experience in the first years of life, the review has adopted a broad, holistic approach. Not only are early childhood policy and

provision the focus of the study, but consideration is also given to the roles of families, communities and other contextual factors influencing children's early learning and development. In particular, the review is investigating concerns about quality, access and equity, with an emphasis on policy development in the following areas:

regulation; staffing; program content and implementation; family engagement and support; funding and financing.

4. As part of the review process, each country hosts a review team for an intensive case study visit. After each country visit, the OECD produces a short Country Note that draws together background materials and the review team's observations. The present report for the USA will be one input into the final OECD Comparative Report that will provide a review and analysis of ECEC (early childhood education and care) policy in all 12 countries participating in the review.³

The U.S. Department of Education, Office of Educational Research and Improvement (OERI) in cooperation with U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Office of the Assistant Secretary for Planning and Evaluation (ASPE) and the Head Start Bureau. During the course of the visit, the team met with many of the major actors involved in ECEC policy and practice in three different states—Colorado, North Carolina, and Ohio—and with representatives from federal government departments and national professional organizations in Washington DC. The team also had the opportunity to observe numerous examples of early childhood programmes and services for children aged 0 to 6 years in Colorado, North Carolina, and Ohio.

1 Early childhood organizations play a pivotal role in shaping the lives of young children. The period from birth to age 5 is critical for a child's brain development, social-emotional growth, and cognitive abilities. Research shows that children who receive high-quality early education and care have better outcomes in school and life. Early childhood organizations provide a nurturing environment where children can explore and learn, enhancing their overall development.

2 Special education organizations play a vital role in ensuring that every child, regardless of their abilities, receives the support they need to succeed. These organizations employ specialized educators and therapists trained to work with children with diverse learning needs. They develop personalized education plans that address each child's unique strengths and challenges.

3 High-quality early childhood organizations prioritize the provision of developmentally appropriate education and care. They follow evidence-based practices and strive for continuous improvement. Quality education and care ensure that children receive appropriate support to reach their developmental milestones and prepare them for academic success.⁴

These organizations go beyond simply providing a safe and nurturing environment. They carefully design their curriculum to meet the unique needs of young children. The curriculum is based on the latest research in child development and incorporates various engaging and age-appropriate activities. The curriculum covers many areas to support holistic development, from sensory play to early literacy and numeracy skills.

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Moreover, effective early childhood organizations understand the importance of individualized learning. They recognize that each child is unique and has different strengths and areas for growth. Therefore, they tailor their teaching strategies to meet each child's needs, ensuring that they receive the necessary support to thrive.

4 The qualifications and training of early childhood educators are vital for delivering high-quality programs. Effective organizations ensure that their staff members have the qualifications, knowledge, and skills to meet the unique needs of young children. They provide ongoing professional development opportunities to enhance the educators' expertise.

These organizations value the importance of continuous learning and growth for their staff. They invest in professional development programs focusing on the latest research and best practices in early childhood education. Educators can expand their knowledge and refine teaching techniques through workshops, conferences, and training sessions.

5 An accumulation of research across hundreds of studies shows the benefits of quality early childhood care and education for children's later learning, school success and social development. In recognition of the value of providing early learning opportunities, many nations have expanded early childhood care and education in recent years. Mexico provides an interesting case in which expansion of early childhood care and education has occurred in the past 5 years, as have initiatives to improve quality and revise the national curriculum for preschoolers. In Mexico between 2000 and 2006 - preschool expansion, quality improvement and curricular reform. ⁵The preschool expansion included a mandate for all parents in Mexico to send their preschool-aged children (3, 4 and 5 years old) to preschool, with target dates of 2004, 2005 and 2008 for 100 per cent coverage of 5-year-olds, 4-year-olds and 3-year-olds, respectively. The quality improvement initiative was part of a larger programmer providing supplemental funds to select preschools and schools in Mexico's public education system. Finally, the curricular reform instituted a new preschool curriculum to be implemented nationwide for all programmers across the 3- to 5-year-old age range.

Portugal has undertaken Monetization and Supervision of Curriculum Development in Preschool Education (2006). The Directorate General for Innovation and Curriculum Development hired the University of Oporto to carry out a case study with 20 kindergartens to collect data on the quality of actual practices of how curriculum guidelines have been used. The results of the study are practical: they call for more support materials, teacher training sessions on the assessment methods of children and their learning environments, more documentation, and strategies to facilitate transition into the first cycle of primary education; and they identify target areas as experimental science, writing skills and mathematics. ⁶

In recent decades, fundamental changes have taken place in the system of preschool education gave, teaching at this stage of the educational process,

has a serious impact on upbringing and problems? Literally 5-6 years ago, preschool education was on the brink of survival, however significant changes in regulatory, administrative, economic conditions modernization of all levels of preschool education gave Pre-school education

⁵ "PEDAGOGS" international research journal

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opportunity to find his image, in his work meaningful directions that allow you to find enthusiasm and unique the tendency to look for educational methods is clear. The life of preschool education, which has been a habit until recently combining the diversity of building types, curricula and programs variety, related to the introduction of new technologies. Russia current view on the current modernization of education - availability, quality, quality, to preschool education or efficiency sets requirements. Organization of the development of preschool education only to quality changes in the process of implementation of preschool education adding quality and quality to a new level - management mode. It is possible with the production of innovations expressed in the transition.

Early childhood organizations are not just places where children are cared for; they are centers of learning and growth. These organizations employ trained professionals who understand the unique needs of young children and create developmentally appropriate programs. The activities and experiences offered by early childhood organizations are designed to promote physical, cognitive, social, and emotional growth. Children develop essential skills and knowledge through play, exploration, and interactions with peers and caregivers.

One of the key benefits of early childhood organizations is their focus on holistic development. These organizations understand that children are not just empty vessels waiting to be filled with knowledge. Instead, they recognize the importance of nurturing a child's development. By providing a structured and stimulating environment, early childhood organizations foster creativity, curiosity, and a love for learning among young children.

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